

Research Article

A Study on the Working People with Disabilities in Indian Economy: An Analysis

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Abstract

Countries Economic Development depends on Labor Force participation, labour contribution and tireless working nature immensely contribute to economic prospect, but World of work having many issues and challenges, in recent global developments, transitions in the post COVID-19 affected world of work, along with the disabilities people working conditions across the world and in India are actively contributing for economic development, disability hampering world of work across the world and even Indian labour productivity, especially in Indian Informal sector. The present study focused on the people with disabilities, types of impairments, their socio-economic conditions, educational attainment, skills, their employment access, employment status, working conditions, wage outcomes and their economic status across the world and in India. the study also focus on the status of women worker's with disabilities and action taken to improve social justice, policy measures and safety at working place, analysis of International Labour Organisation conventions and policy outcomes. The present study is based on the secondary data and its analysis.

Keywords: Disabilities, Employment, Working Conditions, Policy Measures and women workers.

Introduction:

Countries economic prosperity depends on active labor force participation, labour contribution and tireless working nature, their productivity immensely contribute to economic growth, but World of work having many barriers, in recent global developments, transitions in the post COVID-19, meltdown of supply chain across the world and Russian aggression on Ukrian, Israel and Palestinian war impacted to surge of business, trade slowdown created anxiety in the labour market and forcefully pushed to unemployment in the many countries lack of purchasing power, raise of poverty propelled distress, by these informal workforce are affected at large quantum, In, 2023 Labour force participation developments returned to a pre-pandemic downward trend in Asia also. In the Pacific and Asian region, nearly two-thirds of the Jobs/employments are informal types of employment in the year of 2023, within this region the informality of employment rates varies considerably. In 2023, Asia was witnessed 60.9 per cent of the labour participation, Informality of employments are highest in the south-east Asia (70 per cent), 47 per cent in East Asia and 35 per cent in the Pacific region. Informality affects the Asia and Pacific region at varying degrees for their economic growth and nature of work, created a challenge for prospect of the economic development. Labour force participation, women labour force participation assess the countries Human development index. Socio-

economic developments and declining of poverty in this region, educational attainment has been improved. At the same time women labour force participation in the Asian region increased upward and contributing to the country economic development, specially countries like Asian tigers, India, China, Bangladesh and Taiwan are producing women manual oriented products for the world developed markets.

World Health Organisation(WHO) assessed that 1.3 billion people around the world are experiencing major disabilities in the world of work, the protecting the rights of people with disabilities including in relation to working conditions and employment has been explicitly emphasized under international frameworks. United Nation General Assembly in December 2006 reaffirms “ The rights of persons with disabilities to work, on an equal basis with others which includes the right to the opportunity to gain a living by work freely chosen or accepted in a labour market and work environment that is open, inclusive and accessible to persons with disabilities”, many research studies empirically proved that people with disabilities still facing unfavourable working atmosphere in the labour market compared with others. Indian Labour market is predominately informal labour market, many of the labours are suffering different types of disabilities, people with disabilities are concentrated in lower cadre of jobs and they are facing different kinds of disparities at working place, threats, working in unhealthy working conditions, firing from the employments are common, wages disparities are common.

Review of Literature:

International Labour Organisation (2024) : “A Study on the Employment and wage out comes of people with disabilities”, the working paper investigate the employment and wage disparities between people with and without disabilities, types of disabilities, labour participation of people with disabilities, wage disparities, social security and even their occupational disparities and highlights the legal frameworks of international Labour Organisation at international and national levels. The report also suggested to all countries to implement separate or equal opportunities and equal remuneration for disabled working people.

International Labour Organisation and Institute for Human Development (2024), “ India Employment Report(Youth Employment, Education and Skills)” : the report enlightened the status of Employment trends and current scenario in the Indian Economy, Growth and employment, Challenge of youth employment, education and youth employment, skills and active labour market policies, skills requirement and mismatch of education and production and executive skills in the Indian labour market, status of informal workers and the conditions and also emphases on social justice requirement for these informal workers.

International Labour Organization(2024) ; “ World Employment and Social Outlook”- Trends 2024 : the report concentrated on the resilience of world economy after the covid-19 pandemic, job growth, employment opportunities, rising delicacy, unemployment rates in the different countries, wage rate across the countries, working poverty of labourers, labour policies, discussions to provide social justice.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the employment status of the people with disabilities.
2. To study the working conditions of people with disabilities.
3. To study on social justice through existing policy measures for working people with disabilities.

Research Methodology:

This research study adopted the description of the different method undertaken for the analytical study. The present study ‘A Study on the Working People with Disabilities: An Analysis’ based on the secondary data, these data collected from the different article published in peer reviewed journals, publications of International Labor Organization, analysis of ILO-IHD

(Institute for Human Development) “The Indian Employment Report-2024”, reports of Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy, World bank report, Magazine articles and News Paper articles.

Defining People with disability:

As defined in the International classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF), as approved by the WHO Assembly in 2001, the disability term covers impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions. “Impairments” deals to problems in body functioning deviation or loss. People with disabilities are those who are inactive, limited participation at working place because of physical inability, bad mental condition or health barriers, the statistical definition thus informed by the International Classification of Functioning echoes Article 1 of the 2006 convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which states that “persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others” some relevant examples of disabilities at working places has been identified, these are; Vision difficulties (even wearing glasses at working place), hearing impairments or difficulties, communication expression difficulties, physically handicapped or mobility difficulties at working place for some of the workers, for the situation of walking, climbing stairs or standing for long hours to finish the given production task, handling machines or objects difficulty workers who are does not have both hands or arms unable to work properly, behavioral difficulties such as psychological or emotional problems hampered productive efficiency and workers personal too much care for example dressing sense or beauty consciousness also troubled working capacity.

People with Disability employment status:

The employment status of the people with disabilities playing a pivotal role while assessing the economic conditions across the world and even in Indian Economy, their employment status or Economic Status varies from country to country, but we may find similarities across all countries, on average all over the world people with disabilities are not actively participating in the labour force and they are away from the world of work, they are facing severe unemployment, in developing country like India their participation in the labour activity are only meager. As per the working paper of International Labour Organisation shed light on this, which could prompt people with disabilities to reduce their unemployment and take up any available employment to survive in this competitive world to lead happy life. In the developed countries people with disabilities are engaged in self-employed, the recent empirical study in united states of America confirmed that they choose self-employment for non-monetary reasons (Pagan 2009 ; Gouskova 2020), though it did not rule out the possibility of employer discrimination “pushing” part of the population with disabilities into self-employment (Gouskova 2020). The Educational attainment and employment are mismatching, skills and skill up-gradation promotion activities are not providing at many working places to them. People with disabilities are having irregularity to work due to their health problems or disabilities; it leads to insufficient income, disparities in the wages in many countries, in India the same thing is happening, long working hours cause to many health related consequences. The people with disabilities are having more exposes in the informal nature of jobs or elementary occupations like agrarian jobs in the developing countries and they are not largely engaging in the executive jobs like Managers and professionals, women with disabilities are earning less wage than their male counterparts across the all countries in the world is shows the gender disparities exist in the world labour market.

Disability in the Indian Economy:

Indian Economy is demographic dividend country, population has been exploding after various reforms in the health sector and government measures, birth rate is increasing and death rate drastically decreasing, even mortality rate also decreasing hence population stands in

the first place in the world, incidentally the disability of the people increase, as per the National Sample Survey 76th conducted on “The Survey of persons with Disabilities in India conducted during the period of July-2018 to December-2018, the survey conducted 1,18,152 household, in that 81,004 household in rural area and 37,148 household in the urban area, total 5,76,569 persons were enumerated; the survey finds some of important facts about on disability in the Indian Economy, as per the survey prevalence of disability was 2.2 per cent. Prevalence of disability was higher in male than female population, 2.4 per cent of enumerated population was facing disability, 1.9 per cent of female were facing disability. 52.2 per cent were literates, in age group between 15 years and above, 19.3 per cent had highest education level secondary and above. For the livelihood of the disabilities persons large numbers are accommodating in the informal sector of the Indian Economy, the survey focused on the Labour force participation rate, worker population ratio and unemployment rate among the persons with disabilities, as per the survey findings “persons with disabilities of age 15 years and above, Labour Force Participation Rate in usual status was 23.8 per cent, Worker Population Ratio in usual status was 22.8 per cent and Unemployment rate was 4.2 per cent” the survey reveals that unemployment is negligible number, Labour Force Participation was high and Worker Population Ratio is also high comparatively.

Social Justice for working people with Disabilities:

International Labour Organisation defined the Social justice “Socially Just Society” as one where all human beings have the right to pursue, both their material well-being and their spiritual development in conditions of freedom and dignity, of economic security and equal opportunities”(ILO), to promote sustained, inclusive, productive employment and decent working atmosphere for working people with disabilities paramount at this juncture and in the Indian economy, Social Justice for working people with disabilities promotes economic development. Sympathy and empathy on working people with disabilities in the working place Promotes decent work atmosphere and address inequalities the people with disabilities, even maintain parity among the all labours, promote their participation in the economic activity, earning for themselves, including people with disabilities, women workers with disabilities, equitable opportunities in all kinds of works to people with disabilities, improving their living standards, at present proper enforcement of all labour rights and social justice or social protection including education, lifelong learning, skills up-gradation, training, adequate working conditions required to people with disabilities. Social Justice helps to get rid of poverty, gender inequality, promote them to be well-being in the society, it leads them to live comfortable and take own decisions in their individuals, family affairs.

Conclusion :

The International Labour Organisation resolved many policy measures to act for people with disabilities workers to maintain parity at working place, equal opportunities for persons with disabilities, healthy, competition, equal opportunities for with or without disabilities workers across the world, equal wages, implementation of social justice for all the workers without discrimination. In Indian Economy, Government of India and all the state Governments and Union Territories are making efforts to provide social justice to persons with disabilities, required to full pledged reforms for the persons with disabilities at working places and social security cover and lifelong monetary benefits schemes to disabled working people to promote Indian Economy a Viksith Bharath.

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